

RAPID Enabled Physics-Based Neural Networks for Predicting 3-D Fission Distributions in JSI TRIGA Mark-II Research Reactor

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803662

ABSTRACT

The current methods for high-fidelity simulations of nuclear reactor systems are complex and computationally expensive. To reduce computation time, artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) are being considered. Despite showing promise for solving various neutronics problems, the limited availability of high-fidelity data constrains ML applications to simpler problems or systems. This paper utilizes the RAPID code system for its effectiveness at rapidly producing large quantities of high-fidelity data. This has enabled the development of physics-based neural networks (NN) to predict 3-D fission distributions as a function of CR positions for the JSI TRIGA Mark-II research reactor. We developed a NN architecture that contains two hidden layers, 4400 neurons per hidden layer, with Leaky ReLU activation functions. This model was capable of predicting more than 99% of the fission values in the fuel elements within $\pm 0.5\%$ rel. diff. The model also predicted about 98% of the fission values in the fuel followers within $\pm 10\%$ rel. diff. It was determined that errors in the fuel follower predictions did not significantly impact calculated power peaking factors, which fell within the range of -0.39% to 0.91% rel. diff. Hyperparameter tuning and its effect on model performance is also discussed, with some comparisons to simpler ML models developed in a previous study.

Keywords: Physics-based machine learning, RAPID, fission distribution, control rod

1. INTRODUCTION

The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) within the nuclear industry is advancing rapidly, with neutronics applications focused on predicting the system eigenvalue (k_{eff}) and corresponding neutron flux distributions under varying operating conditions. High-fidelity solutions are currently obtained from complex and computationally expensive codes based on Monte Carlo methods or deterministic techniques applied to the Linear Boltzmann Equation (LBE). To address these limitations, a major focus is leveraging ML to construct fast surrogate models that approximate system behavior. This is possible because ML algorithms learn patterns from data without being explicitly programmed, but their accuracy depends heavily on both the quantity and quality of the training data. Consequently, the limited availability of high-fidelity data constrains purely data-driven ML approaches, making them reliant on the same neutronics codes whose speed they aim to overcome. As a result, most data-driven ML studies have been restricted to simpler 2-D or coarser 3-D problems [1].

To reduce dependence on large training datasets, physics-informed neural networks (PINNs) seek to guide the model towards predictions that are consistent with known physics. PINNs incorporate governing equations into the loss function by calculating physics residuals for a large set of collocation points throughout the phase space [2], while measured or simulated data serve as anchor points to direct the model towards a physical solution. Although PINNs have shown promise for neutron diffusion

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eigenvalue problems, applications to the neutron transport equation are still in the early stages [3]. This is largely due to the LBE's high-dimensionality, global coupling across the entire phase space, and sharp flux gradients at material boundaries, all of which contribute to an extremely complex loss landscape that lead to unstable training and offer no guarantee of converging to the fundamental eigenmode.

The RAPID (Real-time Analysis for Particle transport and In-situ Detection) code system [4] provides a path towards physics-based ML because it is capable of rapidly performing large amounts of accurate, high-fidelity simulations of nuclear reactor systems. Since the RAPID solutions are based on particle transport physics, a purely data-driven ML model is implicitly guided by a data-driven physics residual. In our earlier work [5], RAPID enabled the development of simple ML models to predict k_{eff} and 3-D fission distributions as a function of control rod (CR) positions for the Jožef Stefan Institute's (JSI) TRIGA Mark-II research reactor. In this paper, we extend our prior study by performing hyperparameter tuning and optimization of a neural network model to predict the full 3-D fission distribution, including fuel followers, and compare its performance against some of the previously developed ML models.

2. THE RAPID CODE SYSTEM

The RAPID code system is based on the Multistage Response function Transport (MRT) methodology, which involves partitioning a problem into stages or sub-problems that can be simulated using response functions or coefficients [6]. By pre-calculating these response functions/coefficients as a function of different reactor parameters using a Monte Carlo code, solutions can be obtained by solving a simple linear system of equations in seconds or minutes on a single computer core [4].

RAPID can solve various neutronics problems such as critical [7, 8] and sub-critical systems [9], detector response [10, 11], burnup [12, 13], kinetics [14], and control rod movements [15]. RAPID has also been computationally verified against several benchmarks, including the GBC-32 Cask Benchmark [16] and the Watts Bar Unit 1 Benchmark [17], and experimentally validated using the JSI TRIGA Mark-II research reactor [10, 15]. For criticality problems, RAPID uses a novel combined fission matrix (CFM) method [4], which is a physics-based methodology to calculate coupling coefficients between fission regions. The coupling coefficients allow RAPID to obtain solutions to the LBE by solving a linear system of equations given in matrix form by:

$$\mathbf{F} = \frac{1}{k_{eff}} \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{F} \quad (1)$$

It's spatially discretized form for N fission sub-regions (or cells) is given by:

$$F_i = \frac{1}{k_{eff}} \sum_{j=1}^{N_{cells}} a_{i,j} F_j \quad (2)$$

where F_i and F_j are the fission neutron source in the "destination" cell i and "originating" cell j , respectively, $a_{i,j}$ is the fission matrix (FM) coefficient, and N is the total number of fission sub-regions in the model. The $a_{i,j}$ term is a coupling coefficient between fission sub-regions and represents the number of fission neutrons generated in cell i due to a neutron source in cell j . This coefficient inherently captures the transport phenomena responsible for coupling the two sub-regions. Another important observation from Eqn. (2) is that the fission source, F_i , is a sum of the contribution from all other fission sources, F_j . This is physically intuitive as fission can be induced by neutrons arriving through multiple transport pathways.

The FM coefficients are obtained by performing a series of "independent" Monte Carlo fixed-source calculations in each sub-region j and tallying the number of fission neutrons produced in sub-regions i . Therefore, the FM coefficients are dependent on the system and change if system parameters or conditions are modified, such as by movement of CRs. To perform calculations of CR movement in real-time

and avoid many Monte Carlo fixed-source calculations, RAPID utilizes the Fission Matrix Control Rod "deltas" (FM-CRd) methodology, which has been validated against the ICSBEP benchmark for core 133 of the JSI TRIGA Mark-II research reactor [15]. The FM-CRd methodology is based on the understanding that CRs produce a local and quantifiable change to the FM coefficients. These localized effects can be pre-computed and, for any combination of CR movements, systematically combined to adjust a reference set of FM coefficients without the need for additional fixed-source simulations. Therefore, the necessary FM coefficients are generated only once, and re-used to construct new coefficients.

3. MACHINE LEARNING AND NEURAL NETWORKS

Machine learning (ML) is a subset of artificial intelligence (AI) that "learns" from data without being explicitly instructed, instead relying on mathematical equations that adjust model parameters toward some goal. Within supervised learning, the goal is to bring the ML model's predictions closer to some true value, which is achieved by minimizing a loss function, such as the sum of squared errors (SSE):

$$SSE = \sum_{i=1}^n (\hat{y}_i - y_i)^2 \quad (3)$$

where n is the number of training data points, y_i is the true value of the i^{th} training data point, and \hat{y}_i is the ML model's predicted value for the i^{th} training data point. The loss function drives the "learning" in ML because incremental adjustments are made to a model's parameters in the direction that lowers the loss. Furthermore, the magnitude of the loss determines by how much the parameters are adjusted at each incremental step. During the testing phase, or when comparing different ML models, other loss functions and metrics are used to evaluate model performance.

An important consideration in ML is the selection of model hyperparameters, which differ fundamentally from the model parameters. Hyperparameters are model-specific, user-defined values selected beforehand that affect how a model is trained, whereas parameters are internal to a model and are updated through the training/learning process. Hyperparameter "tuning" is a term used to define the process of varying a model's hyperparameters and comparing its effect on model performance. Different ML algorithms have unique parameters and hyperparameters, including neural networks. Neural networks are sequential models that approximate complex functions by layering and connecting many simple computational units called *neurons*, as shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. The activation of a single neuron taking in three inputs, with associated weights (w), plus a bias term (b), and some activation function (σ).

A neuron takes in multiple inputs, multiplies each one by a corresponding weight (w), and sums the results together along with some bias (b). This sum is referred to as the neuron's pre-activation value and is transformed from input to output by an *activation function* (σ). The output of a neuron, known as its activation, takes on a value within a range determined by the chosen activation function. Accordingly, the weights and bias terms are parameters specific to each neuron and are optimized during the training process. Activation functions constitute a user-defined hyperparameter because they determine how a neuron processes information. Except for the linear activation function, they also introduce nonlinearities that help the network capture complex patterns and behaviors in the data. Fig. 2 shows

four activation functions that take in some pre-activation value along the x-axis and outputs some transformation along the y-axis.

Figure 2. Linear, ReLU, Leaky ReLU, and Sigmoid activation functions.

Figure 3. A four layered, fully connected neural network with labeled input, output, and hidden layers. Highlighted are a set of neuron inputs (red) and a set of neuron outputs (orange).

The power of neural networks to approximate complex functions comes from layering many neurons into a connected network, as shown in Fig. 3. This example neural network contains four layers composed of one input and output layer, and two hidden layers. Apart from the input layer, every neuron in the network has a bias term, an activation function, and weighted connections from all the neurons in the preceding layer. The number of neurons in the input and output layers correspond to the number of input features and target variables in the dataset, respectively, and are intrinsic in every neural network. The number of hidden layers and the number of neurons contained in those layers constitute user-defined hyperparameters that require tuning. Collectively, the neural network learns by iteratively updating each weight and bias in proportion to its contribution to the overall loss through the combined process of backpropagation and stochastic gradient descent (SGD).

4. METHODOLOGY

The JSI TRIGA research reactor is a 250 kW, open-pool light water reactor surrounded by a 30.5 cm thick graphite reflector. Its core consists of U-ZrH fuel elements containing 12 wt. % uranium enriched to 19.9%, along with B₄C control rods. Fig. 4 shows the layout of core 132, which contains 40 fuel rods (red) and four CRs (yellow), labeled transient (T), safety (S), regulating (R), and shim (C). The latter three CRs have fuel followers (FF) that replace the CR with fuel as they are withdrawn from the core. The FFs have the same structure, composition, and active length (38.1 cm) as a regular fuel element in the core.

Figure 4. Core configuration 132 for the JSI TRIGA Mark II research reactor with fuel pins (red), control rods (yellow), and empty (white) locations.

In our previous work [5], we used RAPID to develop a large ML dataset composed of 157,324 high-fidelity 3-D fission neutron distributions for various combinations of CR positions. The dataset was divided into 65,536 training cases and 91,788 testing cases, with each fission neutron distribution represented by 693 fission sub-regions. Of the 693 fission sub-regions, 600 arise from discretizing the 40 fuel elements into 15 axial intervals each, and 93 by discretizing the three FFs into 31 axial intervals each. More axial intervals are used for the FFs to account for their movement, which introduces additional complexity because these intervals may be fully or partially occupied by fuel, or completely replaced by absorber depending on the position of the CRs. This results in discontinuous behaviors of the fission values for the FFs as each axial interval corresponds to a fixed spatial position. Consequently, we separate the analysis between core fission regions, which correspond to the 40 fuel elements, and the FF fission sub-regions.

The hyperparameters tuned for each neural network are summarized in Table I below. Tensorflow, a free and open-source deep-learning library for Python, was used for developing the neural network algorithms. Accordingly, the Adam optimizer, with a learning rate of 0.001, was used during the training process. The Adam optimizer is an adaptive optimization algorithm that adjusts the learning rate used in SGD by considering moving averages of past gradients and their magnitudes. It is meant to accelerate convergence of weights and biases, and improve efficiency by reducing the chance of overshooting some global or local minimum of the loss function.

Table I. Hyperparameters tuned for each neural network.

Hyperparameter	Values Tested
Number of Hidden Layers	1,2,3,4
Neurons per Hidden Layer	500 to 4500 (steps of 100)
Activation Function	Linear, ReLU, Leaky ReLU, Sigmoid

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A total of 656 NN models were trained, each using an input layer fixed at four neurons to represent the CR positions and an output layer fixed at 693 neurons to represent the fission rate in each region of the reactor. A Leaky ReLU activation function was used for the output layer to strictly enforce positive fission values. As discussed in Section 4, a distinction is made between the 600 core fission sub-regions and 93 FF fission sub-regions. Given 91,788 testing cases, the NN model's had to predict 55,072,800 values for the core fission sub-regions and 8,536,824 values for the FF fission sub-regions. To evaluate each model's performance, the percent relative difference (PRD) and mean absolute percent relative difference (MAPRD) were computed using the testing data. Table II summarizes the 10 NN models that achieved the lowest MAPRD in predicting the core fission sub-regions. For each model, the table lists the number of hidden layers (HL), neurons per HL, activation function, min/max PRD, fraction of predicted core fission values within ± 0.5 PRD, and computation times for predicting the entire testing dataset.

Table II. Top 10 performing NN models for predicting core fission regions.

HL	Neurons per HL	Activation Function	MAPRD (%)	Min/Max PRD (%)	Pred. Values within ± 0.5 PRD (%)	Time (s)*
2	4400	Leaky ReLU	0.108	(-1.59, 1.47)	99.15	12.08
2	3100	Leaky ReLU	0.113	(-1.63, 1.42)	98.95	9.78
2	1100	Leaky ReLU	0.115	(-2.26, 1.82)	98.97	4.14
2	3500	ReLU	0.118	(-2.52, 1.94)	98.55	10.67
2	2700	Leaky ReLU	0.129	(-2.13, 1.68)	98.28	8.85
2	800	ReLU	0.130	(-3.46, 2.36)	98.05	3.05
2	2500	Leaky ReLU	0.132	(-2.39, 2.24)	98.41	12.46
2	1100	ReLU	0.138	(-2.82, 2.14)	97.65	4.03
3	4000	ReLU	0.141	(-3.43, 2.46)	97.31	56.92
2	3800	Leaky ReLU	0.142	(-1.69, 1.84)	97.73	10.79

*Intel Core i9-12900 (16 cores, 24 threads, 2.40 GHz base), 64 GB DDR5 @ 4800 MHz, Windows.

Table II shows that while all the top models performed extremely well, the architecture with two hidden layers, 4400 neurons per hidden layer, and Leaky ReLU activations performed the best among them. This model achieved the lowest MAPRD, exhibited a very narrow PRD range, and predicted more than 99% of the core fission values within ± 0.5 PRD. The table also shows that the top performing models used either ReLU or Leaky ReLU activations and typically included two hidden layers, whereas the number of neurons per hidden layer was less predictive of overall performance. All of these models outperformed the k NN-11 model from our previous study [5], which had an MAPRD of 0.16% and a PRD range between (-4.03, 4.67).

All 164 models with a linear activation performed worse than linear regression from our previous study [5], which had a MAPRD of 6.83% and PRD range between (-34.62, 52.31). Similarly, 103 of the Sig-

moid models also performed worse than linear regression, whereas the remaining 61 Sigmoid models performed comparably to the k NN-11 model.

For the FF fission regions, the NN models showed a strong tendency to underpredict the fission values. Consequently, the top Leaky ReLU model, with two hidden layers and 4400 neurons per hidden layer, predicted only about 98% of the FF fission values within ± 10 PRD. In contrast, the k NN-11 model exhibited a more balanced mix of overpredictions and underpredictions, yet still predicted only about 96% of the FF fission values within ± 10 PRD. The predictions that exceeded ± 10 PRD were not associated to any specific FF, meaning large errors appeared evenly between the safety, regulating, and shim FFs. However, these large errors tended to occur in FF regions that were partially filled with fuel, where the fission rate drops sharply due to the proximity of the CR. For the top NN model, about 99.7% of the large errors occurred in such regions, whereas for the k NN-11 model this fraction was about 90.8%.

To assess whether the FF errors are acceptable in the context of the full fission distribution, it is important to consider the FF's contribution to the total core fission and how their errors could affect calculation of reactor parameters like power peaking factors. When all four CRs are fully withdrawn or fully inserted, the FFs contribute approximately 7% and 0.6% of the total fission, respectively. The power peaking factors calculated by using the k NN-11 or top NN model's predicted fission distributions were within -0.33% to 1.80% and -0.39% to 0.91% relative difference, respectively. These results demonstrate that errors in the FF regions did not contribute significantly to the error in the power peaking factors.

6. CONCLUSIONS

This paper demonstrated the effectiveness of the RAPID code system to generate the large volumes of high-fidelity data necessary for developing physics-based neural networks capable of predicting 3-D fission distributions as a function of CR positions. Our results highlighted several NN architectures with high performance, with the best performance achieved using a Leaky ReLU activation function, two hidden layers, and 4400 neurons per hidden layer. The best NN model predicted more than 99% of the core fission values within ± 0.5 PRD and about 98% of the FF fission values within ± 10 PRD. Although errors in the FF regions were more pronounced, they were found not to significantly affect the calculated power peaking factors. Nonetheless, methods to further reduce these FF prediction errors are being explored for future model development.

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